

ON THE RELATION BETWEEN SURFACE TENSION AND VAPOUR PRESSURE OF LIQUIDS AND LIQUID MIXTURES

By R. C. TRIPATHI

An equation of the type $\log p = A + \frac{B}{C-\gamma}$ (where p is the vapour pressure, γ is the surface tension of liquids and A , B & C are constants) is proposed and is shown to represent the variation of surface tension of unassociated, associated, organic and inorganic liquids with vapour pressure. The same equation represents the variation of surface tension of binary liquid mixtures of constant composition with vapour pressure.

No relation between the vapour pressure and surface tension of liquids seems to have been worked out. From the Clausius-Clapeyron equation connecting Q (latent heat of evaporation), p (vapour pressure), and T (absolute temperature), it follows that

$$\log p = \frac{-Q}{RT} + A = A + \frac{B'}{T}$$

Since surface tension varies linearly with temperature, at least for short ranges ($\gamma = C - mT$), an equation may be obtained by substituting $(C - \gamma)/m$ for T in the above equation. The equation,

$$\log p = A + \frac{B}{C - \gamma}$$

where A , B and C are constants is obtained.

Table I gives in detail the results for ethyl ether (an unassociated liquid) and ethyl alcohol (an associated liquid). Other results are summarised in Table II where the constants A , B and C^* are given along with the maximum percentage difference and γ range in ($\gamma_{\max.} - \gamma_{\min.}$).

TABLE I

Ether.					Ethyl alcohol.				
γ -range = 30.36. $A = 8.21$. $B = -209.1$. $C = 54.1$.					γ -range = 28.22. $A = 7.78$. $B = -144.2$. $C = 46.2$.				
Temp.	p	γ obs. (dynes.)	γ calc. (dynes.)	% Diff.	Temp.	p	γ obs. (dynes.)	γ calc. (dynes.)	% Diff.
-108°	0.003 mm.	33.25	33.20	0.1	-80°	0.003 mm.	32.21	31.90	0.9
-94.75	0.12	31.58	31.30	0.9	-52.83	0.108	29.12	29.63	1.5
-93.4	0.15	31.23	30.90	1.0	-43	0.25	28.11	28.70	2.1
-85.2	0.33	30.04	30.00	0.1	-22	6.0	25.30	25.77	1.8
-80.4	0.58	29.47	29.40	0.4	-80	812	16.61	16.60	0.0
-63	2.90	27.32	27.13	0.6	100	1692.3	14.67	14.53	0.9
-45.05	13	24.91	24.60	1.3	150	7326	9.52	9.40	1.3
-18.85	63	21.46	21.13	1.3	200	22164	3.99	4.08	2.2
-20	442	16.49	16.50	0.1					
40	648	14.05	14.20	1.0					
50	1276	12.94	13.10	1.1					
60	1728	11.80	12.00	1.6					
70	2294	10.72	10.96	2.1					
80	2991	9.67	9.76	0.9					
90	3840	8.63	8.80	1.7					
100	4859	7.63	7.80	2.0					
150	13280	2.89	2.99	3.0					

TABLE II

Liquid (organic)

	Temp. range.	A.	—B.	C.	Max. diff.	γ-range
cycloHexane	0-70	9.87	423	78.25	0.3%	8.9
Octane	0-100	7.24	161.2	88.70	0.7	10.6
Benzene	0-250	9.43	466.5	82.50	3.2	29.3
Toluene	-92-100	11.19	420.8	80.12	0.1	25.0
o-Nitrotoluene	80-172	6.16	138.6	60.20	0.3	10.6
Chlorobenzene	0-160	7.63	214.2	65.50	0.8	18.6
Bromobenzene	-17-155	7.38	217	69.00	0.6	21.3
Nitrobenzene	53-175	5.26	83.7	53.50	0.1	14.1
Aniline	43-175	5.69	93.9	57.60	0.7	15.6
o-Toluidine	46-154	19.88	194.8	136	0.4	12.8
m-Toluidine	50-150	6.17	112	53.80	0.1	9.9
p-Toluidine	46-126	13.34	706	17.54	0.2	6.5
Ether	-108-150	8.20	209	54.10	1.7	20.4
Carbon tetrachloride	15-250	8.21	251.2	66.60	1.7	24.5
Chloroform	-24-54	12.26	653	91.80	0.4	10.3
Acetone	-91-30	7.32	181.4	58.55	0.8	15.8
Methyl alcohol	-66-200	7.56	130.4	46.30	1.2	27.8
Ethyl alcohol	-80-240	7.76	144.2	46.21	2.5	28.2
Propyl alcohol	-23-100	9.65	205	47.00	0.1	9.6
Butyl alcohol	20-120	7.67	119.2	41.26	0.8	8.3
isoAmyl alcohol	0-130	7.94	135.8	41.40	1.6	9.9
Ethyl formate	-20-210	6.78	101.0	43.95	1.8	23.6
Ethyl acetate	0-80	11.96	661.5	82.50	0.1	8.7
Propyl acetate	-10-210	7.72	178.4	51.90	2.2	22.4
Methyl isobutyrate	0-210	6.62	106.3	44.90	1.2	21.8
Methyl formate	21-200	9.42	414.3	86.10	0.5	23.8
Formic acid	0-130	5.10	49.2	50.70	0.8	13.3
Acetic acid	0-110	20.32	1598	110.40	3.0	10.9
Propionic acid	10-140	8.01	188.6	51.59	0.7	12.7
Butyric acid	10-160	10.19	335.7	59.50	0.1	14.1
Ethyl iodide	0-60	6.27	104.1	52.80	0.7	6.7
Caproic acid	60-130	4.47	37.8	31.56	0.1	6.4
Caprylic acid	120-170	5.12	35.5	27.75	0.1	3.0
Caprylic acid	100-150	6.13	73.8	34.05	0.1	3.8

Liquid (inorganic)

Mercury	20-360	5.29	322.5	511	0.1	95.2
Zinc	490-641	6.13	601	88.70	0.0	27.5
Arsenic trichloride	0-100	7.94	187.2	66.20	0.2	9.5
Sodium fluoride	1396-1557	5.01	191.4	216.1	0.0	14.8
Cesium fluoride	955-1118	1.15	13.8	67.15	0.1	8.0
Phosphorus trichloride	-20-50	9.27	285	68.88	1.0	7.3
Hydrochloric acid	-90-(-77)	11.28	488	81.30	0.5	5.1
Hydrobromic acid	-96-(-68)	10.08	522	98.40	0.2	5.7
Sulphuretted hydrogen (chlorine)	-62-84	4.36	27.15	46.50	0.1	4.7
	-75-50	6.80	127	59.60	0.2	20.15
Helium	-272-(-268)	59.85	-331.8	5.95	2.0	0.3
Neon	-249-(-243)	-0.95	1.15	3.525	1.4	1.6
Oxygen	-205-(-182)	7.27	104.6	36.95	0.7	5.5
Carbon dioxide	-57-30	-9.68	1996	-168.7	0.1	18.1
Sulphur dioxide	0-50	3.73	132.8	64	0.1	0.8
Nitrogen	-106-(-173)	-7.37	86.85	28.17	0.5	7.0
Nitrous oxide	-58-20	27.13	9710	384	1.5	24.6
Water	0-80	5.51	101.4	96.4	0.3	13.2

It is evident from the tables that this equation is very satisfactory. It represents the variations of surface tension with vapour pressure in some cases from very near the freezing point to temperatures much above the boiling point with an error hardly exceeding 1% in most cases and never exceeding 3%. Moreover, the equation is applicable to organic, inorganic, simple and associated liquids,

Another remarkable feature of this equation is that it seems to apply not only to single liquids but also to liquid mixtures (comprising either simple liquids or associated liquids) of fixed composition in the same way as it does in the case of single liquids. The greatest difficulty in verifying this equation in the case of mixtures is that no data are available regarding the surface tension of the liquid mixtures at different temperatures. The values of surface tension of mixtures of any composition at any temperature can be calculated if they obey the mixture law with respect to parachor. A number of such mixtures which obey the mixture law with respect to parachor are known (Hammick and Andrew, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754) and the present work on mixtures has been confined to these only. In Table III the percentage difference refers to the values of surface tension obtained by applying mixture law with respect to parachor and that calculated by this equation.

TABLE III

Temp. range = 0° to 70°.

Ethyl ether in benzene.					Carbon tetrachloride in benzene.					Acetic acid in benzene.				
Mol. fraction.	A.	-B.	C.	Max. diff.	Mole fraction	A.	-B.	C.	Max. diff.	Mol. fraction.	A.	-B.	C.	Max. diff.
0.0	9.43	406.5	82.50	3.0%	0.0	9.43	406.5	82.50	3.0%	0.0	9.43	406.5	82.50	3.0%
0.2356	11.68	644.5	93.55	0.1	0.1	11.19	596.5	92.80	1.2	0.1	6.62	133.9	55.90	0.1
0.4267	11.76	655.0	90.40	0.1	0.5	-5.98	485.0	-34.20	0.2	0.5	11.47	633.5	97.60	0.1
0.7469	8.50	231.0	58.10	0.3	0.9	13.50	898.5	104.60	0.1	0.9	9.43	386.0	81.30	0.1
1.0	8.20	209.0	54.10	2.0	1.0	8.21	251.2	69.60	1.7	1.0	20.32	1598.0	110.40	3.0

All the data for surface tension and vapour pressure have been taken from Landolt Bornstein Tabellen (1923 Edition and subsequent additional volumes).

The author is grateful to Professor B. Prasad for his kind interest and help.

MAYURBAJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE,
CUTTACK.

Received February 23, 1943.